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Grain quality

Distribution of high density and low density grains in the panicle

A. R. Gomosta, H. A. Quayyum, A. H. Molla, and M. Z. Haque, Plant Physiology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

Increasing the number of high density grains (HDG) can increase yield potential of a variety. Varieties differ in the number of HDG per panicle. In a medium grain variety, most spikelets on the primary rachis branches are HDG and those on the secondary or tertiary rachis branches are low density grains (LDG). This study was conducted to find the distribution of HDG and LDG in relation to different grain sizes.

We collected 50 panicles at maturity from each of four varieties: BR11, BR25, BR5, and Tulsimala. From each panicle, grains on the primary rachis branches, secondary rachis branches, and tertiary rachis branches were hand-threshed and separated into HDG (specific gravity of

Distribution of filled grains in the panicles of varieties with different grain sizes.^a

^aGrain size: length × breadth (in mm) BR11 = 16.06, BR25 = 11.57, BR5 = 9.22, and Tulsimala = 8.14.

1.2 or more) and LDG (specific gravity of less than 1.2).

Most of the grain weight of panicles with coarse grain, (BR11), medium grain (BR25), and fine grain (BR5) was attributed to HDG. However, LDG mainly made up the panicle weight of a fine-grained variety (Tulsimala) (see figure). The spikelet numbers per panicle were 248 ± 10 for BR11, 270 ± 10 for BR25, 264 ± 10 for BR5, and 363 ± 10 for Tulsimala. Most of the LDG in Tulsimala appeared on secondary and tertiary rachis branches. The position of HDG and LDG probably depends on grain size and variety. Secondary and tertiary rachis branches contributed significantly to the panicle weight compared with primary rachis branches. ■

A simple, low-cost, on-farm technique for accelerated aging of rice

S. Jesudas and S. Neelakantan, Food Science and Nutrition Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, India

Freshly harvested grain of all rice varieties exhibits poor cooking and organoleptic properties and cooks to a pasty, sticky mass. Aged rice is highly

preferred because of its excellent cooking and organoleptic characteristics. However, the natural aging process takes at least 3-4 mo and requires proper storage. We undertook this study to explore techniques for aging rice that could be practiced in households without much investment or technical competence.

IR50 and ADT36 rice samples harvested during late January 1993 were shade-dried and milled in a modern rice mill. From 100 kg of rice, IR50 yielded

60.2 kg head rice, 18.5 kg broken rice, and 21.3 kg bran and hull mixture, and ADT36 yielded 60.2 kg head rice, 18.2 kg broken rice, and 21.6 kg bran and hull mixture.

Sixteen-kg capacity metal tins were coated with blackboard paint on the outer surface and lids to enhance their heat absorption capacity (see figure). The tins were then filled with rice. Two small closed cups with perforated lids were filled with water and left in the rice at

Changes in the physicochemical, cooking, and organoleptic characteristics of rice varieties due to accelerated aging.

Variety	Aging period (d)	Cooked volume (ml)	Total soluble solids ² of gruel (g%)	Cooking time (min)	Volume expansion ratio	Length elongation ratio	Organoleptic scores ^b		Amylose ^a content (g%)	Amylase ^c activity (units)	Starch ^d (g%)
							Texture of cooked rice	Overall acceptability			
IR50	0	26.0	6.6	23.0	4.0	1.5	2.5	2.5	10.8	09.1	75.8
	6	29.0	5.5	26.0	4.8	1.6	3.0	3.0	12.6	21.8	73.9
	10	33.0	3.7	26.6	5.4	1.7	4.0	3.0	17.0	36.4	70.4
ADT36	0	25.0	6.5	23.0	4.1	1.5	2.0	3.0	10.1	10.9	70.0
	6	28.5	5.3	26.0	4.7	1.5	3.0	3.0	13.1	21.8	68.1
	10	33.0	3.7	27.0	5.4	1.7	4.0	4.0	17.8	36.4	64.5

¹g/100 g rice, ²Maximum score is 4, ³mg maltose produced during 15 min with 1% starch.

equidistance. Tins were kept in direct sunlight from 0800 to 1700 h, thus exposing rice to moist heat as the water evaporated.

During the experiment, the temperature of rice in the tin was 40-44°C and the ambient temperature was 30.8-39.7°C. A sample of rice was drawn from each tin at a 2-d interval and analyzed for changes in physical, chemical, cooking, and organoleptic properties (see table).

During 10-d of accelerated aging, cooked volume, cooked weight, volume expansion ratio, length elongation ratio, amylose content, and amylase activity increased and showed a positive correlation with the number of days of aging, while the total soluble solids of the gruel and breadth elongation ratio decreased. Amylase activity caused starch content to decrease.

Accelerated aging improved all qualities of the rice much more than did naturally aging rice for 90 d. No insect attack was noticed in either the control or the accelerated aged rice samples after being stored for 90 d. The accelerated aged rice samples did not give off a smell or go rancid during storage. This simple, low-cost technique may be practiced in rural and urban households. ■

Setup used for the accelerated aging of rice.

Pest resistance—diseases

Development of near-isogenic lines as international differentials of the blast pathogen

Zhongzhuan Ling, Institute of Crop Breeding and Cultivation, Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences (CAAS), Beijing, China and IRRI; T. V. Mew, IRRI; Jiulin Wang and Cailin Lei, CAAS; and N. Huang, IRRI

The existing differential sets for classifying pathogenic races of *Pyricularia grisea* cannot be used commonly in different rice-growing regions of the world. Some differential sets consist of rice varieties with various genetic backgrounds. For differential sets consisting of near-isogenic lines (NILs), the recurrent parents used carry resistance genes. Therefore, results of patho-

genic race analysis in different areas may not be comparable. To overcome these problems, we need an international set of differentials, each with a single major gene in a common highly susceptible background. We initiated our attempt to develop such a differential set by identifying a highly susceptible rice variety, which was then used as a recurrent parent to develop a set of NILs for establishing international differentials.

Lijiangxintuanheigu (LTH) is a local japonica variety from Yunnan Province in China. It is one of the Chinese differentials established in the late 1970s. This variety was test-inoculated by the Collaborative Research Group of All China with 1,739 blast isolates from different rice-growing regions in China from 1976 to 1979. It showed a highly susceptible reaction to all the isolates. Since 1980, the susceptibility of LTH has been tested in various provinces and autonomous regions of China. No

Table 1. Isolines, parents, genotypes, and homozygous lines tested at IRRI.

Isoline	Donor parent	Genotype	Recurrent parent	Number of resistant lines (BC ₇ F ₃)	Homozygous lines tested
F-80-1	Kusabue	<i>Pi-K</i>	LTH	22	1
F-98-7	Tsuyuake	<i>Pi-K^m</i>	LTH	67	1
F-124-1	K1	<i>Pi-ta</i>	LTH	55	1
F-128-1	Pi No. 4	<i>Pi-ta²</i>	LTH	14	1
F-129-1	K60	<i>Pi-K^p</i>	LTH	53	1
F-145-2	BL 1	<i>Pi-b</i>	LTH	14	1